

FIR Studies of Copper(II) Monohaloacetates : Molecular Structure Based on Cu-O Vibrations

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FIR studies of copper(II) acetate monohydrate, fluoroacetate dihydrate, chloroacetate tetrahydrate and bromoacetate monohydrate have been made in crystalline state at room temperature and at low temperature. The number of Cu-O bands, active in ir, have been calculated theoretically for different possible moieties around Cu atom in the complexes and compared with the total number of bands actually observed in the spectra. A tentative assignment of Cu-O bands have been proposed. On the basis of shifting of Cu-O stretching bands, bridged cage type mode of coordination of the carboxylate ligand to the Cu atom and dimeric bridged cage structure of the complexes have been established.

THE mid infrared region of copper(II) monohaloacetates have been studied extensively and the work done upto 1978 has been reviewed by Nakamoto¹ and Catterick *et al*². In most of these studies attention was focussed on the shifts of asymmetric and symmetric carboxylate stretching vibrations. Some earlier workers³⁻⁸ assigned a series of bands in the frequency region 400-250 cm⁻¹ in copper(II) acetate complexes. However, no attempt has been made to establish or to support the molecular structures of these complexes based on Cu-O vibrations. In our earlier communication⁹, we established the dimeric bridged cage structure of some copper(II) *n*-alkanoates, including selection rules to calculate the Cu-O (carboxylate) vibrations in different possible moieties, comparing them with the total number of vibrations actually observed in the spectra of complexes and tentative assignments of Cu-O bands were also proposed, based on normal coordinate analysis. In the present communication an attempt has been made to establish the molecular structures of hydrated copper(II) fluoroacetate, chloroacetate and bromoacetate by studying Cu-O vibrations.

Experimental

The complexes were synthesised by standard methods¹⁰. The fir spectra were recorded in the region 400-80 cm⁻¹ with a Polytech FIR 30 Fourier spectrophotometer. The spectra were recorded at 298 and 77°K. The samples were prepared in wig-shaped polyethylene pellets, obtained by mixing 5.0 mg of a complex with 40 mg powdered polyethylene and pressing.

Results and Discussions

The number of vibrations of the different possible moieties immediately around the Cu atom in the

studied complexes have been summarized in Table 1 which shows possible molecular structure, possible moieties around the Cu atom, point-group, type of fundamental vibrations allowed by selection rules and the total number of vibrations, which should be active in the spectrum of the complex.

The total number of bands observed in the spectra of the complexes are shown in Table 2. The identification of the bands were made by comparing the spectra of copper(II) haloacetates with those of corresponding sodium salts except those which looked like mixed band, on the basis of increased intensity of the band. All the bands (stretch and bending) due to Cu-O vibrations are believed to lie in the range between 200-500 cm⁻¹. However, to be sure that no relevant band had been overlooked, the supplementary bands below 200 cm⁻¹ were also looked for. No supplementary band was observed except in the case of Cu(ClCH₂COO)₂.4H₂O.

It is obvious from Table 2 that hydrated copper(II) monohaloacetates show, on the average, 4 bands which agree well with a pyramidal CuO₄ moiety (Fig. 4.2) belonging to C_{4v} point group. We have no exact data about the coordination place of H₂O molecule in these complexes. It is, therefore, considered only tetravalent copper moieties showing the number of bands closest to the observed average 4 and at the maximum 6. Thus the monomeric and dimeric transplanar moieties, CuO₂X₂ (Fig 4.4), and the dimeric square planar structure having CuO₄ and CuX₄ moieties together (Fig. 4.3 and 4.8) need further consideration. To reach clearcut conclusions some other factors should also be taken into account. The monomeric *trans*-planar structure (Fig 4.4) may not be accepted for the

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following reasons :

1. It can not explain spin-spin transition i.e. the subnormal magnetic moment of copper(II) fluoroacetate dihydrate, chloroacetate tetrahydrate and bromoacetate monohydrate are 1.38, 1.45 and 1.48 B.M. respectively^{11,12}.
2. The existence of band at 375 m μ in uv absorption spectra which is diagnostic of dimeric structure¹³.

3. The ΔE (difference between asym. and sym. COO stretching bands) should be much higher, as infact, it has an asymmetrical oxygen and halogen linked bidentate structure, which means a monodentate structure of each COO group. The ΔE values are 195,205 and 202 cm⁻¹ for monofluoro, monochloro and monobromoacetates respectively, which are quite close to 184 cm⁻¹ for copper(II) acetate monohydrate¹⁴.

TABLE 1—CALCULATIONS OF Cu-O VIBRATIONS IN DIFFERENT POSSIBLE MOIETIES

Molecular structure	Possible moiety	Structure	Figure No.	Point group	Types of vibrations allowed by selection rules	Total no. of active bands
Dimeric bridged cage type ; Cu atom bonded to oxygen O ⁻ - HYDROXYL OXYGEN 	CuO ₂	Square pyramidal	4.1	C _{4v}	3A ₁ + 2B ₁ + B ₂ + 3E	6
	CuO ₄	Square pyramidal	4.2	C _{4v}	2A ₁ + 2B ₁ + B ₂ + 2E	4
	CuO ₄	Square planar	4.3	D _{4h}	A _{1g} + B _{1g} + B _{2g} + A _{2u} + B _{2u} + 2E _u	3
Monomeric ; Cu atom bonded to oxygen and halogen (X). X - HALOGEN 	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Trans-planar</i>	4.4	D _{2h}	2A _g + B _{1g} + 2B _{1u} + 2B _{2u} + 2B _{3u}	6
	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Cis-planar</i>	4.5	C _{2v}	4A ₁ + 3B ₂ + A ₂ + B ₁	8
	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Trans-pyramidal</i>	4.6	C _{2v}	4A ₁ + 2B ₂ + A ₂ + 2B ₁	8
	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Cis-pyramidal</i>	4.7	C _s	5A' + 4A''	9
Dimeric bridged cage type : Cu atom bonded to oxygen and halogen (X) 	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Trans-planar</i>	4.4	D _{2h}	2A _g + B _{1g} + 2B _{1u} + 2B _{2u} + 2B _{3u}	6
	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Cis-planar</i>	4.5	C _{2v}	4A ₁ + 3B ₂ + A ₂ + B ₁	8
	CuO ₄	Square planar	4.3	D _{4h}	A _{1g} + B _{1g} + B _{2g} + A _{2u} + 2E _u	3 + 3 = 6
	CuX ₄	Square planar	4.8	D _{4h}	A _{1g} + B _{1g} + B _{2g} + A _{2u} + 2E _u	8
	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Trans-pyramidal</i>	4.6	C _{2v}	4A ₁ + 2B ₂ + A ₂ + 2B ₁	9
	CuO ₂ X ₂ & CuX ₄	<i>Cis-pyramidal</i>	4.7	C _s	5A' + 4A''	9
Dimeric bridged cage type : Cu atom bonded to oxygen and halogen (X) 	CuO ₂ X ₂	<i>Square-pyramidal</i>	4.8	C _{4v}	2A ₁ + 2B ₁ + B ₂ + 2E	4 + 4 = 8
	CuX ₄	<i>Square-pyramidal</i>	4.9	C _{4v}	2A ₁ + 2B ₁ + B ₂ + 2E	8

Fig. 3. Dimeric structure

Vibrations in italics are active in infrared.

TABLE 2—TOTAL NUMBER OF Cu-O BANDS OBSERVED IN THE SPECTRA OF COMPLEXES IN THE REGION 500-100 cm⁻¹

Compound	Temp.	Number of bands between 500-100 cm ⁻¹	Total number of bands observed
Cu(CH ₃ CO ₂) ₂ ·H ₂ O	RT	1vs + 3s + 1br sh + 1w	4-5
	LT	1vs + 3s + 2m	5-6
Cu(CH ₂ FCO ₂) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	RT	2s + 2m + 1s mix + 1	5-6
	LT	3s + 1m + 1s mix + 1mw	5-6
Cu(CH ₂ ClCO ₂) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	RT	1vs + 2s + 1m mix + 1vw	4-5
	LT	1vs + 2s + 1s mix + 1w	4-5
Cu(CH ₂ BrCO ₂) ₂ ·H ₂ O	RT	1vs + 1mw + 1vs mix + 2s	4-5
	LT	1vs + 2s + 1vs mix + 1m + 1vw	5-6

vs = very strong, s = strong, m = medium, mw = medium weak, vw = very weak, w = weak, br = broad, sh = shoulder, mix = mixture, RT = Room temp. (298°K), LT = Liquid nitrogen temp. (77°K).

Fig. 4.1 Moiety-CuO₄ square pyramidal point group-C_{4v}.

Fig. 4.2 Moiety-CuO₄ square pyramidal point group-C_{4v}.

Fig. 4.3 Moiety-CuO₄ square planar point group-D_{4h}.

Fig. 4.4 Moiety-CuO₂X₂ trans-planar point group-D_{2h}.

Fig. 4.5 Moiety-CuO₂X₂ cis-planar point group-C_{2v}.

Fig. 4.6 Moiety-CuO₄X₂ trans-pyramidal point group-C_{2v}.

Fig. 4.7 Moiety-CuO₄X₂ cis-pyramidal point group-C_s.

Fig. 4.8 Moiety-CuX₄ square planar point group-D_{4h}.

Fig. 4.9 Moiety-CuX₄ square pyramidal point group-C_{4v}.

Fig. 4. Various possible moieties immediately around the copper(II) atom.

The dimeric moieties having *trans*-planar moiety, CuO₂X₂, (Fig. 4.4) belonging to D_{2h} and square planar moieties, CuO₄ and CuX₄ (Fig. 4.2 and 4.8) having D_{4h} point groups, do also not seem reasonable because of the following reasons :

1. If the molecule has D_{2h} type structure, then all the stretching and bending vibrations will involve halogen (X) atoms except Cu-O stretching vibrations.

Thus a bending Cu $\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Cu} \\ \diagup \\ \text{X} \end{matrix}$ must be at lower frequency than the bending

Cu $\begin{matrix} \text{O} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{Cu} \\ \diagup \\ \text{O} \end{matrix}$ because F, Cl, Br atoms are heavier

than oxygen. In D_{4h} symmetry, 3 vibrations would be due to CuO₄ moiety and 3 to CuX₄ moiety. Thus, 3 vibrations can be in the range of CuO₄ and 3 in the lower range of frequency.

2. The moiety D_{2h} would imply that practically all the stretching vibrations should show their frequencies in the decreasing order Cu-O > Cu-F > Cu-Cl > Cu-Br. A similar trend should be obtained for bendings also. In D_{4h} moiety 3 vibrations should remain fixed and another 3 of planar CuX₄ moiety should show low frequency shifts in the order F > Cl > Br.

3. Both of these moieties have bendings with only one COO oxygen atom, which should also give much higher ΔE values than for bridged cage structures including CuO₄ moieties with bands due to the 2 oxygen atoms of each COO group.

Fig. 5. Comparative chart of copper(II) haloacetates.

A comparative chart of fir region 500-200 cm⁻¹ is presented in the Fig. 5. The arguments outlined above can be checked against the trend seen from this figure, taking (CH₃COO)₂Cu.H₂O as the reference.

For D_{2h} moiety, the vibrations should be shifted towards lower frequency in view of points 1 and 2. It is, however, found that monofluoro, monochloro and monobromo compounds have most of the bands shifted to higher frequencies in the sequence fluoro < chloro < bromoacetate. This contradicts the possibility of a dimeric moiety belonging to D_{2h} point group. This conclusion is also supported by ΔE values¹⁴, which are in the range of dimeric bridged cage compounds. All these evidences discard a dimeric structure with local moiety having D_{2h} symmetry around Cu atom.

point for group; as ν_a(Cu-O) > ν_s(Cu-O) > δ_a(O-Cu-O) > δ_s(O-Cu-O).

In Fig. 5, we have presented the comparative chart of copper(II) fluoroacetate, chloroacetate and bromoacetate. The assignments of bands have been made by the proposed theoretical sequence and shown in Table 3. The bands at 364, 370 and 385 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of copper(II) fluoroacetate, chloroacetate and bromoacetate are assigned to ν_a(Cu-O) vibrations, whereas bands at 310, 317 and 330 cm⁻¹ are assigned to the ν_s(Cu-O) vibration for the respective compounds. Recently, Faniran *et al*^{3,5} have assigned the bands at 364 and 324 cm⁻¹ for ν(Cu-O) vibrations in copper(II) fluoroacetate. The bands at 385 and 330 cm⁻¹ were assigned to stretching modes of Cu-O band in the copper(II) chloroacetate.

TABLE 3—TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENT OF BANDS IN COPPER(II) MONOHALOACETATES

Assignments	Cu(FCH ₂ CO ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Cu(ClCH ₂ CO ₂) ₂ .4H ₂ O	Cu(BrCH ₂ CO ₂) ₂ .H ₂ O
ν _a (Cu-O)	364 s	370 s	385 s
ν _s (Cu-O)	310 m	317 m	330 m
Ring deformation + δ _a (O-Cu-O)	288 s	276 s mix	269 vs
Ring deformation + δ _s (O-Cu-O)	248 m	257 m	248 m mix
Torsion	226 s br mix	233 w	226 w
Lattice vibrations	198 m	182 s	187 small
	170 mw	174 m	170 s

For D_{4h} symmetry, some vibrations should be at nearly fixed positions in monofluoro, monochloro and monobromo compounds and some should decrease in the order acetate > monofluoroacetate > monochloroacetate > monobromoacetate. However, we did not find either any fixed vibrations nor any band decreasing from acetate to monobromoacetate. These observations obviate the possibility of local D_{4h} symmetry. A similar conclusion is arrived for the point 3 due to low ΔE values which are in the range for the dimeric cage compounds. It is thus concluded that the structure of hydrated copper(II) monohaloacetates should correspond to the CuO₄ moiety with local C_{4v} symmetry (Fig. 4.2).

Tentative assignment of bands: It has been established that in copper(II) acetate monohydrate the moiety immediately around the copper atom is CuO₅ in which the Cu atom is slightly above the plane of the four oxygen atoms making the square pyramidal structure. The four eventual oxygen atoms are at the corners of a square base and the fifth oxygen atom is coordinated to the Cu atom at the transaxial position. The fifth O* atom is of different nature as is shown in Fig. 1. The Cu atom is linked to the other Cu atom by only a very weak δ-interactions. No Cu-Cu bond has, therefore, been considered. The CuO₅ moiety belongs to C_{4v} pointgroup. The fundamental vibrations and their sequence for the CuO₅ moiety of the Cu(CH₃COO)₂.H₂O are: ν_s(Cu-O*) > ν_a(Cu-O) > ν_s(Cu-O) > δ_a(O-Cu-O*) > δ_a(O-Cu-O) > δ_s(O-Cu-O).

On the basis of similar grounds, we named the fundamental vibration and proposed their sequence for copper(II) monohaloacetate, belonging to C_{4v}

It is obvious from Table 3, that both of ν_a(Cu-O) and ν_s(Cu-O) bands shifted to the higher frequency region in the sequence Cu-BAC > Cu-CAC > Cu-FAC; where BAC stands for bromoacetate, CAC for chloroacetate and FAC for fluoroacetate. This sequence leads us to suggest that ν(Cu-O) vibrations decrease with an increase in electronegativity of the R group. This would indicate the weakening of Cu-O bond from bromoacetate to fluoroacetate. A similar behaviour was observed by Nakamoto *et al*¹⁵ for copper(II) acetyl acetonate and copper(II) hexafluoroacetylacetonate. They observed that substitution of CF₃ for CH₃ caused the Cu-O stretching band to shift to a lower frequency. Very recently, Faniran *et al*³ studying the mono-, di- and trifluoroacetate have pointed out that the Cu-O bond weakens with the increase in the electronegativity of R group. On the other hand the frequency separation of ν(Cu-O) vibration [Δν(Cu-O)] is found practically constant for the haloacetates (54, 53 and 55 cm⁻¹) for copper(II) fluoroacetate, chloroacetate and bromoacetate. The same trend was observed for the ΔE(ν_aCOO - ν_sCOO) in these complexes. Therefore, the dimeric bridged cage structure can be established for these complexes.

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